

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FOR SPACE ECOSYSTEM - EU-RISE

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ABSTRACT

The emerging space ecosystem is expected to grow significantly, with more than 40,000 satellites and 100 lunar missions envisioned to be launched over the next decade. This extensive infrastructure will subsequently drive the demand for capabilities to transport, assemble in-orbit and maintain this infrastructure for future use. In parallel, the advancement of space robots has cleared the door for new capabilities for in-space maintenance, assembly, and manufacturing (ISAM). These capabilities present considerable business prospects while also promising to improve the efficiency and robustness of the orbital infrastructure. It will create an entirely new market and has the capacity to establish a new space ecology.

The European Robotics for Space Ecosystem (EU-RISE) project aims to advance the robotic and autonomous technologies required for in-orbit manufacturing, assembly and servicing (e.g. refuelling, payload exchange) up to the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5.

To achieve this, the project has two interrelated sub-goals: the definition of the future space ecosystem and the development of an end-to-end, laboratory demonstrator integrating all the enabling technologies. This paper focuses on detailing the approach and results of the first sub-goal with a first description of the architecture of the envisaged demonstrator, including hardware and software aspects.

1. INTRO ISMA

The market for in-space manufacturing and assembly (ISMA) and on-orbit services (OOS) is currently taking shape and could reach several billion euros by 2023-2032. The upcoming space ecosystem is expected to undergo significant growth, with over 40,000 satellites and 100 lunar missions anticipated to be launched in the next ten years. This extensive infrastructure will

subsequently drive the demand for capabilities to transport, assemble in-orbit and maintain this infrastructure for future use.

To address this market appropriately, it is essential to develop in-orbit assembly and servicing capabilities combined with a logistic architecture. Robotic technologies is a key enabler of this market as it allows to unlock mandatory mission capabilities for services and assembly in space.

2. PROJECT'S GOALS

EU-RISE is a 24-month research & innovation action funded by the European Union. The project draws upon the maturation of space robotics that has paved the way for new capabilities for in-space servicing, assembly and manufacturing (ISAM). These capabilities offer significant business opportunities and promise to increase the efficiency and resilience of the orbital infrastructure.

EU-RISE has two objectives: firstly, to carry out a market analysis for space services, space assembly and manufacturing and related areas and to develop two reference scenarios that will be analysed and used to define an end-to-end approach. Secondly, to use the end-to-end concept to bring the building blocks and relevant robotic elements to maturity and to establish an open-source strategy for the further maturity of these building blocks.

EU-RISE contributes to Europe's positioning as a leader in the global space industry. The establishment of a European ISAM capacity and defining the future space ecosystem will have a significant impact. By developing and implementing these new capabilities, Europe can maintain its competitiveness on the global stage, create new jobs, and drive economic growth through increased investment in the space industry. Furthermore, the development of a sustainable space ecosystem will have

a positive impact on the environment, reducing the amount of waste and pollution in space and contributing to a more sustainable and cleaner space environment.

The EU-RISE consortium is composed of 9 partners from 6 countries. Airbus Defence & Space GmbH is leading the project and the 7 other partners of the projects by alphabetic order are Airbus Defence & Space Ltd, Airbus Defence a Space SAS, DFKI GmbH, Libre Space Foundation, Magellium SAS, Oikoplus GmbH, Sener SA, The Exploration Company GmbH.

3. FUTURE SPACE ECOSYSTEM ASSESSMENT AND DEFINITION

This first workstream focuses on assessing future space ecosystem markets, including logistics, on-orbit services, manufacturing, and sustainability. It also involves defining robotic services and architecture for future space systems, investigating transportation and logistics, developing modular receiving services and exploring open-source software development for space qualifies applications.

Market and economic analysis were used to identify new market opportunities for a future space ecosystem. The required services and associated capabilities were then defined, leading to the definition of market and mission requirements. A system concept definition was then carried out, leading to a realistic concept of a laboratory demonstrator for a specific reference use case of the previously identified in-space manufacturing and assembly mission.

This study showed that to address the different markets and missions identified, a modular approach in terms of robotic capabilities, transportation and interface seems mandatory. To this end, the main functions required to address future on-orbit service missions have been identified and arranged in a modular concept. This concept is based on building blocks that are arranged differently depending on the mission to be addressed, resulting in a trade-off between versatility and specific needs.

Based on this analysis, it's clear that modular designs of future space-elements are essential whether in the definition of service vehicles or in the future client infrastructure. Indeed, a modular function implementation is key to cover a wide range of ISAM missions.

On robotic system side, the list of all the building blocks needed to address the market has been established and derived into physical building blocks covering multiple functions. A total of seven physical building blocks are needed in order to cover all the functions identified. The fact that physical building blocks need to address different functions and adopt a modular approach will bring some constraints on the design definition and the

physical building blocks identified so far are: robotic manipulators, vision system, robotic control unit, robotic tools, workbenches, part dispenser, standard interfaces.

Figure 1 : Reusable by re-entry concept

These different building blocks has been designed with a modular approach allowing to introduce them in different concepts. Indeed, two different concepts and associated mission scenarios have been selected to cover mid/short timeframe market evolution and long-term market evolutions. In the short/mid-term scenario also called “re-usable by re-entry”, a servicing vehicle composed of a capsule with re-entry capabilities and a servicing module is used to perform different kinds of ISAM missions.

Figure 2 : In orbit modular concept

After each mission or group of missions, the elements that can be reused for future missions are stored in the re-entry capsule to be recovered on ground. The design of the servicing module may differ depending on the mission to perform but a modular implementation of the functions will allow it to cover the different missions. In the long-term scenario also called “In-orbit modular”, a modular servicing vehicle composed of different building blocks is used to perform different kinds of OOS/OOA missions.

Figure 3 : Reusable by re-entry concept of operations example

The assembly of modules forming the servicer may differ from one mission to the other. The assembly of modules is reconfigurable in space so the servicer can perform different kinds of missions.

This approach is compatible with most of the OOS/OOA missions foreseen and the physical elements that have been identified need to be further developed to address this future space ecosystem. Indeed, this approach showed that the application is not the predominant aspect as the modularity is addressed at building block level to cover different missions. These two-reference scenario are used to construct the end-to-end demonstration scenario presented in the next chapter.

4. END TO END DEMONSTRATOR

The second workstream aims to define an end-to-end demonstrator that includes the capabilities needed for the future commercial and institutional space market. The system is built for all relevant components from special development for the space market in order to achieve a high degree of system integration and maturity.

The selected applications for this demonstration ranging from reconfiguration/payload-exchange to the robotic assembly of an antenna reflector. The execution of the test shall be completed in a realistic setting with respect to lightning conditions, and the situational awareness of the operator.

Figure 4 : In orbit modular concept of operations example

To achieve this goal the displayed testbench is covered in a darkening cloak to eliminate every external light sources. The only visible light existing will be generated by an array of special LED to produce parallel light mimicking the sun light in orbit to generate shadows and high contrast similar to the space illumination conditions. Specialized cameras with filters are used as observation system for a safety operator to ensure the operations are safe.

Figure 5: In orbit modular concept

This operator will be different from the operator commanding the system and is just responsible for observation and ensure the system is safe or engage with activation of the emergency stop. The testbench is equipped with a three-axis gravity offloading system that is used to reduce the weight for the payloads in order to allow robotic operations with the flight manipulator on earth. The operator of the robotic system will see just the telemetry data which will be used within the digital twin to visualize the system status and the tree camera streams from the two tool cameras and the scene camera.

5. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES – HARDWARE

The EU-RISE project will make use of existing hardware building blocks to compose a realistic robotic system mimicking a potential flight system capable of addressing a wide range of relevant services such as refuelling, capturing, assembly and servicing. In addition to adapted components with a high maturity the demonstration will relay on mock-ups for non-core elements. The following list is providing an overview of the elements used for the EU-RISE project:

- High TRL Elements:
 - VISPA Manipulator
 - Multi-Purpose Tool (MPT)
 - Tool Sockets
 - SIROM C Standard Interconnect
 - SIROM G Refuelling Interconnect (TBC)
 - RCU
- Mock Ups:
 - Tool Magazine
 - Antenna Part Dispenser
 - Refuelling Payload
 - Antenna Workbench for Assembly

The robotic tool and tool sockets will be adapted to the EU-RISE specific needs during this activity. The SIROM

interfaces and the VISPA Manipulator will be produced for the EU-RISE project.

Figure 6: Hardware Building-Blocks

6. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES – SOFTWARE

Figure 7: Software Building-Blocks

7. CONCLUSIONS

EU-RISE aims to establish a European capacity for on-orbit services and in-space manufacturing to promote industrialisation and business in space, while supporting low-cost missions and a sustainable, circular economy in space. It will develop new technologies and concepts for space systems and services, enabling in-orbit demonstration/validation and mature key technologies contributing to Europe's independence in space technology development.

Overall, the project's influence on Europe is varied and extensive, encompassing economic growth, job creation, technical innovation, and environmental stewardship. By developing a European ISAM capacity and defining the future space environment, Europe can position itself as a global space industry leader while also paving the road for a more sustainable and prosperous future.

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10. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AOCS: Attitude and Orbit Control System

EU-RISE: European Robotics for Space Ecosystem

ISMA: In-Space Manufacturing and Assembly

LEO: Low Earth Orbit

OOS: On-Orbit Services